

Morphological characterization of Amaranth germplasm

Taslima Jahan^{1*}, *Md. Sadiqur Rahman*², *Syed Md. Mizanur Rahman*³

¹Scientific officer, Plant Genetic Resources Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bangladesh

²Scientific officer, Seed Technology Division, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bangladesh

³Principal Scientific officer, Horticulture Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bangladesh

***Corresponding author**

Taslima Jahan

Email: taslimawrc@yahoo.com

Mobile: +8801718647697

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Abstract: To know about the phenotypic diversity of 42 accessions of amaranth (*Amaranthus* spp), an experiment was designed in the experimental field of Plant Genetic Resources Centre of BARI, Gazipur during 2016-17. The germplasm were classified on the basis of their use. Among them, 6 germplasm were identified as leaf amaranth and the rest 36 were stem amaranth. Amaranth were also classified as hard (14.29%), medium (4.76%) and soft (80.95%) on the basis of fiber. Qualitative variation was found in branching index, stem and leaf pubescence, leaf shape, leaf margin, terminal inflorescence shape, terminal inflorescence attitude and inflorescence density index. Different color variations were exhibited in stem (green-23.81% and pink or purple-76.19%), leaf pigmentation (entire lamina purple-7.14%, margin and vein pigmented-38.10%, normal green-26.19%, more green shade on purple leaf-9.52%, more purple shade on green leaf-16.67% and light green colour-2.38%), petiole (green- 38.10%, purple- 50.0% and dark purple-11.90%), inflorescence (green-76.19%, purple-19.05% and dark purple-4.76%) and seed (brown-4.76% and black- 95.24%) colour. The maximum co-efficient of variation was obtained from the length of top lateral branches (34.57%) followed by their lateral branches length (33.14%) and the terminal inflorescence lateral length (32%). The 1000 seed weight of the collected germplasm varied within 2.45 to 4.5g.

Key words: Amaranth, Qualitative variation, leaf pigmentation

Introduction:

Amaranth is the name given to a group of approximately 70 species of annual or short-lived perennial plants in the genus *Amaranthus* including several species of aggressive edible weeds native to the US. The area and production of amaranth is 10,537 ha and 67,964 metric tons, respectively giving average yield as 6450 kg/ha [1]. Though it is grown round the year but its production is mainly concentrated during summer when no other green vegetables are available in the market [2]. Amaranth is a fast growing crop and because of its low

production cost, it is one of the cheapest dark green vegetable in the tropical market and is often described as the poor man's vegetable. This vegetable can grow under varied soil and agroclimatic conditions [3], and is also resistant to heat and drought with no major disease problems [4]. Besides its adaptable nature in various climatic conditions, the amaranth plant is crammed with excellent nutritional and medicinal values [5,6,7] that help to maintain for the proper functioning of human body. It contains proteins, carbohydrates, many vitamins like Vit-A, B₁, B₆, C and K and is also rich in different minerals like iron, copper, magnesium, potassium, calcium and phosphorus, crucial for maintaining the necessary balance of electrolytes in the body. Moreover, due to the presence of more dietary fiber and protein, it helps to improve bowel movement, aids digestion, reduces LDL levels in the blood and instigates weight loss. Amaranth leaves instigate coagulation and have been known to boost up blood hemoglobin content and RBC counts. However, the PGRC is maintaining 731 accessions, 79 new collections and some previous collections of amaranth. The present study has been designed to study the genetic diversity, to identify useful traits and to produce sufficient seeds of amaranth for the gene bank.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at the Plant Genetic Resources Centre of BARI, Gazipur during winter 2016-17. Forty two germplasm of amaranth were used in this study. Line sowing was done in 3m long of 5 rows plot with two replications. Row to row distance was 50 cm and plot to plot distance was 100 cm. The seeds were sown on 05 December, 2016. Chemical fertilizers such as urea 250 kg/ha, TSP 100 kg/ha, MP 150 kg/ha and gypsum 75 kg/ha were applied [8]. The half quantity of urea and all TSP, MP and gypsum were applied during land preparation. Urea was applied in two equal installments at 20 and 40 days after sowing. Plants of one replication were isolated with nylon net to control cross pollination and the seeds were collected from this plants. Normal cultivation techniques and intercultural operations were followed to have a good crop. During the experiment, some insect's infestation namely leaf folder and thrips were recorded as major pest of amaranth. To control leaf folder Malathion was sprayed @ 1.5 ml/liter for 3 times at 15 days interval and for thrips control Aktara (0.25g/l) and Vertimec (1.2ml/l) were sprayed alternately at 10 days interval for 2 times. Some plants were also attacked by root rot and leaves of most of the germplasm were infected showing white rust symptom. To control root rot, Tilt 250 EC (0.05%) was sprayed surrounding the collar region and for controlling white rust, Redomil gold (0.2%) was sprayed for 2 times. Data were recorded as per IBPGR descriptors for amaranth (1981).

A. Qualitative descriptor

1. **Classes of amaranth:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
 - 1 - Leaf amaranth, 2 - Stem amaranth and 3 - Grain amaranth
2. **Stem softness of amaranth:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
 - 3 - Soft, 5 - Medium and 7 - Hard
3. **Germination rate:** Data was recorded at germination stage.
 - 2 - Slow (2 – 7 days) and 3 - Very slow (> 7 days)

4. **Growth habit:** Data was recorded 4 weeks after seed germination.
1 - Erect and 2 - Prostrate
5. **Branching index:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
2 - Few branches (all near the base of the stem), 3 - Many branches (all near the base of stem) and 4 - Branches all along the stem
6. **Stem pubescence:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
0 - None and 7 - Conspicuous
7. **Stem pigmentation:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
1- Green and 2 - Purple or pink
8. **Spines in leaf axils:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
0 - Absent
9. **Leaf pubescence:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
0 – None and 3 - Low
10. **Leaf pigmentation:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
1- Entire lamina purple or pink,
6 - Margin and vein pigmented
8 - Normal green,
10 - More green shade on purple leaf,
11 - More purple shade on green leaf and
12 - Light green colour
11. **Leaf shape:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
1- Lanceolate 2 - Elliptical, 3 - Ovate, 4 - Rhombic and 5 - Oval
12. **Leaf margin:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
1 - Entire and 2 - Crenate
13. **Prominence of leaf veins:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage.
2 - Rugose (veins prominent)
14. **Petiole pigmentation:** Data was recorded at vegetative stage
1- Green, 3 - Purple and 4 - Dark purple
15. **Terminal inflorescence shape:** Data was recorded at flowering stage.
1 - Spike (dense), 2 - Club-shaped at tips and 4 – Other (spike-lax)
16. **Terminal inflorescence attitude:** Data was recorded at flowering stage.
1 - Erect and 2 - Drooping
17. **Presence of auxiliary inflorescence:** Data was recorded at flowering stage.
2 - Present
18. **Inflorescence density index:** Data was recorded at flowering stage.
3 - Lax, 5 - Intermediate and 7 - Dense
19. **Inflorescence color:** Data was recorded at flowering stage.
2 - Green, 5 - Purple and 6 - Dark purple
20. **Seed color:** Data was recorded after sun drying of mature seed.
1- Brown and 3 - Black
21. **Seed coat type:** Data was recorded after sun drying of mature seed.
2 - Opaque
22. **Seed shape:** Data was recorded after sun drying of mature seed.

1 - Round

B. Quantitative Descriptors

23. **Germination period:** Number of days from sowing to first germination was recorded.
24. **Plant height (cm):** Mean height of 10 randomly selected plants was measured at flowering stage.
25. **Days to flowering:** Number of days required from sowing to first flower opening of 50% plant.
26. **Length of basal lateral branches (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected basal lateral branches was measured at vegetative stage.
27. **Length of top lateral branches (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected top lateral branches was measured at vegetative stage.
28. **Leaf length (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected leaves was measured at vegetative stage.
29. **Leaf width (cm):** Mean width of 10 randomly selected leaves was measured at vegetative stage.
30. **Terminal inflorescence stalk length (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected of terminal inflorescence stalk was measured at flowering stage.
31. **Terminal inflorescence lateral length (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected of terminal inflorescence lateral length was measured at flowering stage.
32. **Length of axillary inflorescence (cm):** Mean length of 10 randomly selected of axillary inflorescence was measured at flowering stage.
33. **1000-seed weight (g):** Weight of 100 randomly selected seeds was measured after sun drying and then multiplied by 10.

Results and discussion

Qualitative Descriptors

Qualitative characteristics of different accessions of amaranth have been exhibited in Table 1. At the beginning, the germplasm were classified on the basis of their use. Among them, 6 germplasm were identified as leaf amaranth and the rest 36 were stem amaranth. On the basis of fiber quality, amaranth were also classified as hard (14.29%), medium (4.76%) and soft (80.95%) type. Thirty five germplasm germinated slowly and the rest 7 come out very slowly. Most of the germplasm (37) exposed erectly and the others (5) showed prostrate type growth habit. Among the collected materials, only one germplasm had no branch, 6 had many branches near the base of the stem and the rest 35 germplasm had branches all along the stem. Having pubescence in plant part mostly acts as a defensive organ against insect pest [9]. Most of the germplasm (97.62%) including in this experiment had conspicuous pubescence on the stem and low pubescence was observed in the lower surface of leaves (95.24%). Maximum (76.19%) germplasm showed purple or pink coloured stem and minimum (23.81%) germplasm showed green colour. Spines in leaf axils was absent in all the germplasm. All the germplasm showed different pigmented leaf such as a few had entire lamina purple or pink (7.14%), some had leaf with pigmented margin and vein (38.10%), some exposed with normal green (26.19%), some had more green shade on purple leaf (9.52%), more purple

shade on green leaf (16.67%) and light green colour (2.38%). Lanceolate (4.76%), elliptical (54.76%), ovate (35.71%), rhombic (2.38%) and oval (2.38%) leaf shape were found among the germplasm. Leaf margin showed entire (97.62% accessions) and crenate (2.38%) phenomena among the germplasm. Rugose leaf veins were found in all accessions. Petiole pigmentation green (38.10%), purple (50%) and dark purple (11.90%) occurred among the accessions. Most (52.38%) of the germplasm showed lax types spike of terminal inflorescence shape, some general spike (10%) and the rest (23.81%) accessions were club-shaped at tips. Terminal inflorescence attitude was erect (47.62%) and drooping (52.38%). Auxiliary inflorescence was present in all the collected materials. Inflorescence density index was found such as lax (11.90%), intermediate (35.71%) and dense (52.38%). The plants of all germplasm flourished with different colour inflorescences visually, green (76.19%), purple (19.05%) and dark purple (4.76%) colour. Maximum (95.24%) germplasm produced black seed color and the rest 4.76% exhibited brown color. The seeds with opaque coat having round shape were found in all the germplasm.

Quantitative characters

Major yield contributing characters of different collected germplasm with some statistical value have been presented in Table 2. The germination period of all germplasm varied from 4 to 11. On an average, the plant height was 137.68 cm. Days to 50% flowering ranged from 60-108 days. The length and width of leaf were 18.59 and 9.64 cm, respectively. Terminal inflorescence stalk length varied within 5.87 to 20.42 cm whereas the lateral length ranged from 0.78 to 3.10 cm. The length of auxiliary inflorescence varied within 4.93 to 16.10 cm. The maximum co-efficient of variation was obtained from the length of top lateral branches (34.57%) followed by their lateral branches length (33.14%) and the terminal inflorescence lateral length (32%). The 1000 seed weight of the collected germplasm varied within 2.45 to 4.5g.

Table1. Qualitative characteristics of amaranth accessions

Name of Descriptor	Descriptor state	No. of acc.	Percent of acc.
Classes	Leaf amaranth	6	14.29
	Stem amaranth	36	85.71
Stem softness	Hard	6	14.29
	Medium	2	4.76
	Soft	34	80.95
Germination rate	Slow	35	83.33
	Very slow	7	16.67
Growth habit	Erect	37	88.10
	Prostrate	5	11.90
Branching index	No branches	1	2.38
	Many branches	6	14.29
	Branches all along the stem	35	83.33
Stem pubescence	None	1	2.38
	Conspicuous	41	97.62
Stem pigmentation	Green	10	23.81
	Purple or pink	32	76.19
Spines in leaf axils	Absent	42	100
Leaf pubescence	None	2	4.76
	Low	40	95.24

Name of Descriptor	Descriptor state	No. of acc.	Percent of acc.
Leaf pigmentation	Entire lamina purple or pink	3	7.14
	Margin and vein pigmented	16	38.10
	Normal green	11	26.19
	More green shade on purple leaf	4	9.52
	More purple shade on green leaf	7	16.67
	Light green colour	1	2.38
Leaf shape	Lanceolate	2	4.76
	Elliptical	23	54.76
	Ovatainate	15	35.71
	Rhombic	1	2.38
	Oval	1	2.38
Leaf margin	Entire	41	97.62
	Crenate	1	2.38
Prominence of leaf veins	Rugose	42	100
Petiole pigmentation	Green	16	38.10
	Purple	21	50
	Dark purple	5	11.90
Terminal inflorescence Shape	Spike	10	23.81
	Club-shaped at tips	10	23.81
	Spike-lax	22	52.38
Terminal inflorescence attitude	Erect	20	47.62
	Drooping	22	52.38
Presence of axillary inflorescence	Present	42	100
Inflorescence density index	Lax	5	11.90
	Intermediate	15	35.71
	Dense	22	52.38
Inflorescence color	Green	32	76.19
	Purple	8	19.05
	Dark purple	2	4.76
Seed color	Brown	2	4.76
	Black	40	95.24
Seed coat type	Opaque	42	100
Seed shape	Round	42	100

Table2. Quantitative variation of different characters in amaranth germplasm

Character	Range	Mean	SD	CV%
Germination period	4 - 11	6.19	1.92	30.95
Plant height (cm)	84.6 -181.8	137.68	20.68	15.02
Days to 50% flowering	60-108	87	10.31	11.81
Leaf length (cm)	8.13 - 25.81	18.59	2.94	15.82
Leaf width (cm)	4.99 - 13.74	9.64	1.84	19.12
Length of basal lateral branches (cm)	20.2 - 67.22	40.52	13.43	33.14
Length of top lateral branches (cm)	8.07 - 34.71	21.21	7.33	34.57
Terminal inflorescence stalk length (cm)	5.87 - 20.42	12.66	3.50	27.67
Terminal inflorescence lateral length(cm)	0.78 - 3.10	1.46	0.47	32
Length of axillary inflorescence (cm)	4.93 - 16.10	10.00	2.06	20.64
1000-seed weight (g)	2.45– 4.5	3.60	0.65	18.10

Conclusion

Though wide variations were found in both qualitative and quantitative characters among the germplasm, some collected materials exposed same attitude in terms of qualitative phenomena such as AC-48, AMA-295, AMA-356, AMA-366 and AMA-377 had the same and AHI-42, AHI-47, AHI-55 and AHI-88 manifested as same and again the germplasm AC-108, AC-164, AHI-44 and AC-511 exhibited the same characters. So, it would be better if those germplasm could be studied under molecular characterization to get a confirmed result. Again, as still now, the maximum people of Bangladesh receive amaranth just for leaf and stem purpose, those germplasm could be better that invite late reproductive stage. With this point of view, the germplasm AC-126, AC-310, AC-511, AHI-25, AMA-131, AMA-134 and AMA-417 can be accepted for consumer use but all the germplasm should be preserved having other good performance and to enrich gene bank for future study.

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Appendix

Table1. Listing qualitative characters of different accessions of amaranth

Coll. No.	Classes of amaranth	Stem softness of amaranth	Germination rate	Growth habit	Branching index	Stem pubescence	Leaf pubescence	Leaf margin
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
AC 32	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 48	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 70	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 87	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 108	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 126	2	3	3	1	4	7	3	1
AC 164	2	3	3	1	4	7	3	1
AC 211	2	5	3	1	1	7	0	1
AC 219	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 221	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 310	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 359	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 412	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 438	2	3	3	1	4	7	3	1
AC 496	1	7	2	1	4	0	0	2
AC 505	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AC 511	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AHI 25	2	5	2	1	4	7	3	1
AHI 42	1	7	2	2	3	7	3	1
AHI 44	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AHI 47	1	7	2	2	3	7	3	1
AHI 55	1	7	2	2	3	7	3	1
AHI 88	1	7	2	2	3	7	3	1
AHI 93	2	3	3	1	3	7	3	1
AMA 05	2	3	3	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 43	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 52	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 131	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 134	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 209	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 235	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 271	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 284	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 289	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 295	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 326	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1

AMA 334	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 356	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 366	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 377	2	3	3	1	4	7	3	1
AMA 417	2	3	2	1	4	7	3	1
RAI 297	1	7	2	2	3	7	3	1

Table1. Cont'd

Acc. no.	Prominence of leaf veins	Petiole pigmentation	Spines in leaf axils	Leaf shape	Stem pigmentation	Leaf pigmentation	Terminal inflorescence Shape
	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
AC 32	2	4	1	5	2	10	5
AC 48	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AC 70	2	1	1	5	1	8	4
AC 87	2	1	1	2	1	8	5
AC 108	2	3	1	2	2	6	4
AC 126	2	1	1	5	2	11	5
AC 164	2	3	1	2	2	6	4
AC 211	2	3	1	6	2	8	5
AC 219	2	1	1	2	1	8	5
AC 221	2	1	1	5	1	8	5
AC 310	2	3	1	5	2	10	4
AC 359	2	3	1	2	2	10	5
AC 412	2	3	1	2	2	6	5
AC 438	2	4	1	5	2	1	1
AC 496	2	4	1	7	2	1	5
AC 505	2	4	1	5	2	6	5
AC 511	2	3	1	2	2	6	4
AHI 25	2	3	1	2	2	6	5
AHI 42	2	1	1	2	2	11	5
AHI 44	2	3	1	2	2	6	4
AHI 47	2	1	1	2	2	11	5
AHI 55	2	1	1	2	2	11	5
AHI 88	2	1	1	2	2	11	5
AHI 93	2	1	1	2	1	8	5
AMA 05	2	3	1	5	2	8	5
AMA 43	2	3	1	5	2	10	5
AMA 52	2	4	1	5	2	1	5
AMA 131	2	1	1	5	1	8	4
AMA 134	2	1	1	5	1	8	4
AMA 209	2	3	1	2	2	11	4

AMA 235	2	3	1	2	2	6	5
AMA 271	2	1	1	1	1	8	1
AMA 284	2	1	1	5	1	8	5
AMA 289	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 295	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 326	2	1	1	5	2	6	1
AMA 334	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 356	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 366	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 377	2	3	1	2	2	6	1
AMA 417	2	3	1	5	2	11	4
RAI 297	2	1	1	1	1	12	5

Table 1. Cont'd

Acc. no.	Terminal inflorescence attitude	Presence of axillary inflorescence	Inflorescence color	Inflorescence density index	Seed color	Seed coat type	Seed shape
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
AC 32	1	2	5	3	5	2	1
AC 48	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 70	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 87	1	2	2	5	5	2	1
AC 108	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 126	1	2	5	5	5	2	1
AC 164	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 211	2	2	5	5	5	2	1
AC 219	2	2	2	5	5	2	1
AC 221	1	2	2	5	5	2	1
AC 310	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 359	2	2	2	3	5	2	1
AC 412	2	2	2	5	5	2	1
AC 438	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AC 496	1	2	6	3	4	2	1
AC 505	2	2	2	5	5	2	1
AC 511	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AHI 25	1	2	2	7	5	2	1
AHI 42	1	2	5	5	5	2	1
AHI 44	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AHI 47	1	2	5	5	5	2	1
AHI 55	1	2	5	5	5	2	1
AHI 88	1	2	5	5	5	2	1
AHI 93	1	2	2	3	5	2	1
AMA 05	1	2	2	5	5	2	1
AMA 43	1	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 52	1	2	6	7	5	2	1
AMA 131	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 134	2	2	2	5	5	2	1

AMA 209	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 235	1	2	2	5	5	2	1
AMA 271	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 284	1	2	2	5	5	2	1
AMA 289	2	2	2	7	4	2	1
AMA 295	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 326	1	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 334	1	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 356	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 366	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 377	2	2	2	7	5	2	1
AMA 417	1	2	5	7	5	2	1
RAI 297	1	2	2	3	5	2	1

Table 2. Listing quantitative characters of different accessions of amaranth

Acc. no.	Germination Period (days)	Plant height at flowering stage (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Terminal inflorescence stalk length (cm)	Terminal inflorescence lateral length (cm)	Length of axillary inflorescence (cm)
	1	2	3	4	5	6
AC 32	5	154.4	90	12.78	1.36	9.56
AC 48	4	166	91	18.23	1.66	10.50
AC 70	5	134.2	96	11.12	3.1	7.60
AC 87	5	137.4	75	12.20	1.16	10.87
AC 108	6	165	91	19.52	1.76	10.14
AC 126	10	114.6	99	5.87	1.24	4.93
AC 164	10	157.4	96	9.95	1.12	10.96
AC 211	11	159.8	65	18.07	1.32	12.31
AC 219	4	139.8	75	10.63	1.04	9.19
AC 221	6	152.4	79	10.82	1.08	9.67
AC 310	6	158.2	106	12.55	1.32	10.96
AC 359	5	140.6	91	11.33	1.18	6.34
AC 412	5	123.6	86	11.50	0.78	11.07
AC 438	10	138.2	86	13.15	1.4	10.76
AC 496	4	137.8	60	11.08	0.94	13.49
AC 505	4	116	81	11.33	1.66	5.21
AC 511	5	127.4	99	6.87	1.44	9.71
AHI 25	6	130.2	105	6.95	1.5	9.14
AHI 42	6	111.2	86	8.15	1.36	9.00
AHI 44	6	181.8	90	14.13	1.24	10.07
AHI 47	5	135	96	10.12	1.22	9.91
AHI 55	6	126.2	86	10.77	1.18	9.36
AHI 88	6	121.2	90	10.53	1.4	9.53
AHI 93	10	97.2	77	11.68	1.34	10.40

AMA 05	10	131.2	80	9.62	1.3	9.86
AMA 43	6	113.6	77	14.28	1.26	10.33
AMA 52	6	116.8	77	17.75	1.38	16.10
AMA 131	5	124.2	100	10.43	2.54	7.89
AMA 134	5	131.6	100	11.03	3	8.49
AMA 209	7	128.2	87	12.72	1.06	10.86
AMA 235	6	135.6	91	16.32	1.06	13.57
AMA 271	5	148	81	9.37	1.86	8.93
AMA 284	6	158.6	83	12.17	1.3	6.71
AMA 289	6	111.6	87	15.60	1.72	9.57
AMA 295	5	166.2	87	20.42	1.58	11.64
AMA 326	5	173.4	89	14.82	1.3	10.14
AMA 334	6	139.6	89	17.87	1.52	11.87
AMA 356	6	142.2	87	15.38	1.7	10.11
AMA 366	5	158.2	87	17.17	1.7	11.64
AMA 377	10	146	89	14.08	1.58	11.19
AMA 417	5	147.2	108	8.63	1.42	9.43
RAI 297	6	84.6	71	14.62	1.2	10.91

Table2. Cont'd

Coll. No.	Basal lateral branches	Top lateral branches	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	1000 Seed weight (g)
	7	8	9	10	11
AC 32	54.46	34.71	19.31	10.67	4.5
AC 48	42.34	20.71	20.97	9.27	4
AC 70	33.18	18.43	18.54	11.20	4
AC 87	54.54	18.86	13.47	6.74	3.65
AC 108	28.13	25.14	18.97	12.00	3
AC 126	50.38	22.71	17.57	12.13	3.5
AC 164	33.06	31.29	21.10	11.77	4.5
AC 211	20.2	22.03	8.13	5.07	3.55
AC 219	49.54	29.57	18.70	11.17	3.6
AC 221	64.67	22	17.30	9.04	2.75
AC 310	37.14	31.56	20.26	11.03	3.35
AC 359	33.22	13.27	20.81	11.13	4.5
AC 412	36.37	31.5	21.10	10.31	3.15
AC 438	35.48	27.43	18.97	11.06	4.5
AC 496	67.22	24.13	10.53	6.26	2.9
AC 505	37.38	27.42	18.71	11.27	4.5
AC 511	39.69	13.71	17.84	7.87	2.8
AHI 25	44.14	34.29	20.04	9.47	4.5
AHI 42	52.47	20.44	18.39	9.53	4.5
AHI 44	50.17	12.57	21.73	9.13	3.5
AHI 47	62.61	21	20.07	10.44	3.5

AHI 55	45.68	25.01	18.91	10.57	4
AHI 88	47.17	22.87	17.90	10.90	3
AHI 93	61.59	25.3	19.00	9.76	2.9
AMA 05	60.49	18.42	18.54	9.74	3.5
AMA 43	57.14	24.43	17.51	9.41	3.1
AMA 52	57.15	23.36	17.79	9.49	4.5
AMA 131	39.49	8.1	18.66	11.41	2.6
AMA 134	24.69	8.5	18.97	9.44	4
AMA 209	22.12	13.59	18.76	8.79	4
AMA 235	36.47	26.01	19.69	9.70	4.5
AMA 271	24.05	19.8	17.70	7.04	4
AMA 284	27.97	8.07	18.11	9.26	3.5
AMA 289	30.97	9.18	15.43	9.67	2.5
AMA 295	27.99	18.79	19.44	10.39	2.85
AMA 326	47.87	25.92	25.81	13.74	2.45
AMA 334	27.85	19.93	20.99	8.00	2.8
AMA 356	22.34	15.77	18.43	7.76	3.5
AMA 366	21.55	13.81	20.10	8.70	4
AMA 377	26.26	17	21.39	8.54	2.95
AMA 417	29.49	11.37	21.14	11.03	4
RAI 297	37.06	32.8	14.14	4.99	3.7

About the Authors:

	<p>Mrs. Taslima Jahan is currently working as a Scientific Officer at Plant Genetic Resources Centre in Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI). She has completed her Bachelor degree and Masters from Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. She has recently working on morphological characterization of different vegetable.</p>
	<p>Md. Sadiqur Rahman is currently working as a Scientific Officer at Seed Technology Division in Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute. He has completed his bachelor degree from Patuakhali Science and Technology University and Masters degree on Seed Science and Technology from Bangabanghu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University, Bangladesh. Now he has working as a Seed Technologist on BARI. Md. Sadiqur Rahman has developed one variety of citrus (BARI Jara lebu-1)</p>
	<p>Dr. Md. Mizanur Rahman is currently working as Senior Scientific Officer at Horticulture Research Centre in Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bangladesh. He has completed his PhD degree from Bangabanghu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University, Bangladesh. Dr. Md. Mizanur Rahman has developed three varieties of Banana and one variety of Golden apple (BARI kola-3, BARI kola-4, BARI kola-5, and BARI Amra-1).</p>